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**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
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**ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ
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MAIN FACTORS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY AND QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS

Annotation. Higher education today faces important tasks, such as educating and training the younger generation, capable of actively participating in a qualitatively new, rapidly changing stage of development of society, as well as the implementation of priority projects to prepare students for the mastery and practical application of acquired knowledge in the digital economy. The article discusses the need to further improve the education system in the context of socio-political modernization of society.

Keywords: education, modernization, reform, human capital, information technology, competitive personnel, cooperation, educational technology.

ОСНОВНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

Аннотация. Перед высшим образованием сегодня стоят важные задачи, такие как воспитание и подготовка молодого поколения, способного активно включаться в качественно новый, стремительно меняющийся этап развития общества, а также реализация приоритетных проектов по подготовке обучающихся к освоению и практическому применению полученных знаний в условиях цифровой экономики. В статье рассматриваются вопросы необходимости дальнейшего совершенствования системы образования в условиях социально-политической модернизации общества.

Ключевые слова: образование, модернизация, инновации, сотрудничество, человеческий капитал, цифровизация, образовательная среда, научный потенциал.

TA'LIM TIZIMINING SAMARADORLIGI VA SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING ASOSIY OMILLARI

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda oliy ta'lim oldiga jamiyat taraqqiyotining sifat jihatidan yangi, tez o'zgarib borayotgan bosqichida faol ishtirok eta oladigan yosh avlodni tarbiyalash va tarbiyalash, shuningdek, raqamli iqtisodiyotda talabalarni olingan bilimlarini o'zlashtirish va amaliy qo'llashga tayyorlash bo'yicha ustuvor loyihalarni amalga oshirish kabi muhim vazifalar turibdi. Maqolada jamiyatning ijtimoiy-siyosiy modernizatsiyasi sharoitida ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish zarurligi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, modernizatsiya, islohot, inson kapitali, axborot texnologiyalari, raqobatdosh kadr, hamkorlik, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

INTRODUCTION

Attention to the field of education is becoming especially relevant throughout the world in the age of globalization and information technology, when the level of development of a country is determined not only by socio-economic, cultural indicators, assessment of strength and power, but is largely based on its intellectual potential. After all, it is scientific and technological progress, the foundations of which are laid in the educational environment, that is the central link in the sustainable development and prosperity of the country.

To solve the problems of building a new state, it is of fundamental importance to train personnel of a new formation, educated on national, universal values and capable of implementing in practice large-scale tasks of modernizing the country and building a modern democratic society. Practice shows that only that country, that nation can achieve a great future, prosperity and well-being that can prepare knowledgeable, professionally competent and energetic individuals, true patriots of their country, enrich them with the enormous spiritual heritage of the great national culture, and introduce them to the treasures of world culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The path to national revival passes through high education and high culture. That is why the level of education and the degree of professional training should become a measure of the progress of our social development in the 21st century. This is the best guarantee of the successful implementation of the planned course of reforms; this is the direction that, over time, will give the greatest dividends from the invested funds.

The World Bank report "Changing Wealth of Nations" notes that it is human capital, i.e. the totality of knowledge, talents, skills and abilities of people constitutes the main wealth of the country.

Thus, the well-being of developed countries is ensured by human capital by 68%, and in developing countries by only 41%.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Modern experience of Uzbekistan in modernizing the education system. The issue of modernization of education, the implementation of which could ensure a transition to a new type of social development, is especially acute for Uzbekistan.

As is known, modernization is a process of transformation that involves the movement of society towards the most effective model of sustainable development, overcoming economic backwardness, political instability, the development of innovation, the process of creating new technologies, a new system of spiritual values and ideological attitudes.

Modernization of education is a complex multifaceted process, so its implementation should be based on the results of in-depth theoretical research.

One of the important issues of modernization of the education system, requiring philosophical analysis, seems to be understanding the problem of the relationship between various aspects in the theory and practice of training specialists in new socio-economic conditions. To do this, it is important to analyze the socio-philosophical foundations of the modernization of education related to the new picture of the world, as well as the place of man in the modern world. This will make it possible to identify directions for the development of vocational education and reach educational technologies that can transform the sphere of education into the sphere of reproduction of a creative personality.

It is quite obvious that this cannot be accomplished without studying the modern educational situation, the basic principles of the evolution of modern education, analyzing new trends and understanding the ways of transition from the philosophical foundations of the development of education to the practice of its reform.

One of the main characteristics of the modernization of domestic vocational education today is its humanistic orientation, where the center of attention of society and the state is the person as a creatively developing personality.

The main features of modernization in this area are associated with updating the status, goals, content, forms and means of education. The process of modernizing a vocational school involves the creation and implementation of a model of innovative education.

The processes of modernizing the education system of Uzbekistan and training highly qualified personnel also involve the development and implementation of effective organizational, pedagogical forms and means of spiritual and moral education of the younger generation, based on rich national cultural and historical traditions, customs of the people and universal values. Because the task of education is to form the personality of a person capable of empathy; ready for free humanistic ally oriented choice, individual intellectual effort, independent, competent, responsible action in political, economic, professional and cultural life, respecting oneself in others, tolerant of representatives of other cultures and nationalities, independent in judgment, open to different opinions and unexpected thoughts.

Strategy for reform in the field of education, practical steps for implementation. The most important strategic goal of Uzbekistan is to join the number of developed countries in the world and ensure a decent life for its citizens. The country is implementing a clear, clear and deeply thought-out program of action, and the organizational, legal and practical, consistent and systemic measures taken fully contribute to the implementation of democratic, political and economic reforms, social transformations aimed at creating ample opportunities for the science and practice of comprehensive implementation professional, intellectual and spiritual potential of the citizen and society as a whole. In conditions when an educated, politically and socially active person with a high level of legal awareness and culture is assigned the role of the central agent of all changes, the issues of progressive development of the education system become increasingly significant.

In recent years, Decrees and Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been adopted aimed at modernizing the entire system of national education. Particular attention is paid to the issues of reforming the higher education system with an emphasis on increasing the level of scientific and pedagogical potential, compliance with modern requirements of educational, methodological and information support of the educational process [1].

In general, in the period from 2017 to 2021, more than 1.7 trillion soms were allocated for the implementation of measures to improve the higher education system, more than \$203 million of which 1.2 trillion soms (about \$144 million equivalent) - for the construction, reconstruction and overhaul of educational and laboratory buildings, gyms and student accommodation, over 500 billion soms (about 60 million US dollars in equivalent) - for equipping with educational and laboratory equipment, furniture and supplies, the creation of interuniversity shared laboratory complexes, as well as the development of information and communication technologies.

Based on established partnerships with foreign universities, it is planned to annually attract at least 350 foreign highly qualified teachers and scientists to the educational process in universities in Uzbekistan.

At the same time, work is underway to widely introduce advanced pedagogical technologies, curricula and teaching materials based on international educational standards into the educational process. Taking into account the prospects for the integrated development of regions and sectors of the economy, the needs of territorial and sectoral programs, target parameters for personnel training are formed in accordance with higher education, and directions and specialties of training are optimized.

Work is being consistently carried out to solve the problem of creating and introducing new generation teaching aids into the higher education system and providing universities with modern educational and scientific literature. Work has been launched to translate the latest foreign literature into the Uzbek language.

A steady increase in the level and quality of professional skills of teaching staff requires the completion of advanced training courses, internships for

employees, training for graduates of higher educational institutions in PhD and master's programs abroad.

Today, each higher educational institution in the country is developing a specific program in this area.

In September 2018, the «El-Yurt Umidi» Foundation was established in Uzbekistan, aimed at establishing close cooperation with compatriots with great scientific potential, scientists, specialists and talented youth living and conducting their professional activities abroad [2].

The fund is designed to provide Uzbekistan with highly qualified and competitive specialists in the global labor market, necessary for the comprehensive and accelerated development of our country. Its activities are aimed mainly at wide coverage of diligent, purposeful representatives of science, teachers and assisting them in improving their qualifications, both in leading foreign educational institutions and in Uzbekistan itself. At the same time, the goal is to adopt the most progressive world achievements, enrich ourselves with the latest research in scientific thought, and introduce in Uzbekistan all the best from the world practice of using advanced technologies and innovations.

It must be emphasized that the policy pursued by Uzbekistan in the field of education is aimed at ensuring the consistent and systematic implementation of the principles proclaimed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which guarantees the right to free general education.

As you know, on January 28, 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev “On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026” was issued [3]. The fourth priority area of this Strategy is the implementation of a fair social policy and the development of human capital. In particular, in solving problems for the further development of this area, it is envisaged to improve the quality of education in schools and raise the knowledge and qualifications of teaching staff to an international level, by: determining domestic or international certification requirements for each subject for conducting activities in a school; diagnosing the knowledge and skills of school teachers who do not have a category; optimization of regional units of the public education system through complete digitalization of their activities, etc.

If we consider that today the urgent need for scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel alone is more than 5000, this figure will increase at least 50–100 times, if we also take into account the urgent need for scientific and pedagogical personnel in the production spheres. The incompatibility of the education system with the needs of the economy is a serious problem today.

According to a World Bank study, 35% of Uzbekistan faces difficulties in finding qualified specialists with higher education.

To implement these national tasks of training specialists abroad and dialogue with compatriots in 2019, it is planned to allocate 45 billion sums (54 million US dollars in equivalent) from the state budget to the «El-Yurt Umidi» Foundation. In the future, this amount will be increased.

Cooperation in the field of education. Work continues to attract leading foreign universities to open their branches in Uzbekistan. Until 2017, training was organized in the capital's branches of 7 foreign universities, namely Westminster International University, Singapore Institute of Management Development, Turin Polytechnic University, Moscow State University, Russian State Economic University named after V. Plekhanov, Russian Institute of Oil and Gas named after Gubkin, Yuzhno – INHA University of Korea. In 2018 alone, 13 new universities began operating in Uzbekistan, in particular the Silk Road International University of Tourism in Samarkand, a branch of the National Research Technological University MISIS (Russia) in Almalyk and Bucheon University of South Korea in Tashkent. At the Uzbek-Russian educational forum held in October 2018, agreements were reached on the opening of branches of 6 Russian universities and 2 faculties in Uzbekistan, as well as the implementation of 52 joint educational programs. It is planned that in the future the organized faculties will be gradually transformed into branches of the Bulletin of Science and Practice.

In February 2019, an agreement was signed marking the opening of the country's first branch of an American university, Webster University, in Tashkent. Today the university successfully operates and provides a full range of academic programs for both undergraduate and graduate degrees, in particular in the areas of business administration, marketing and entrepreneurship, computer science, journalism and media industry, healthcare management, STEAM education and innovation and other areas training.

To date, the number of universities in Uzbekistan has reached 102, of which 85 are local universities and their branches, as well as 17 foreign higher educational institutions and their branches. By the end of 2019, 13 new universities began operating in the country, including 8 branches of foreign universities, 22 joint faculties, 46 joint educational programs.

Such an increase in the number of universities, including branches of foreign and local universities, as well as the emergence of non-state universities, will help increase the enrollment of young people in higher education and its quality. It should be noted that in the future it is planned to hold educational forums with countries such as France, Germany, Japan, Turkey, China, South Korea and India.

On September 11, 2023, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Strategy “Uzbekistan - 2030” was signed. The strategy includes 100 important goals in five priority areas.

Among the main goals defined in this strategy, special attention is paid to the creation of an education system that fully meets the needs of the people and international standards [3].

Information technology in education. Currently, information technology occupies a central place in education: the emergence of various online courses, educational resources and platforms that complement and compete with traditional educational organizations.

Government subsidies and support amount to billions to create and support digital educational platforms, as well as develop and adapt legislative and technical

policies and initiatives. Digital tools in higher education are becoming an integral part of domestic and global politics and economics.

Digitalization is also having an impact in the academic sphere. The modern higher education system has gone through an extremely important stage of computerization and informatization. It can be noted that the mechanisms of change in the information space were complex, dependent on funding, on the level of higher educational institutions, on the level of readiness of teaching staff, etc.

Information technology plays a huge role in increasing the efficiency of the education process. Unfortunately, it must be noted that today there remains a low level of use of information technology in the educational sphere, both in terms of expanding access and in terms of the use of new teaching methods.

Measures taken to solve these problems will contribute to the widespread use of ICT tools, allowing for much greater flexibility and lower costs in choosing courses for training and mastering the content of relevant specialties provided by higher education. The introduction of modern educational programs, pedagogical and smart technologies into the educational process will help to radically improve the quality of education. It is obvious that a positive imprint on the quality training of highly qualified specialists will be left by the organization of distance classes and seminars, video conferences, which will also contribute to strengthening interactive interaction and cooperation between educational institutions, including foreign ones

Modern digital technologies, media platforms, and electronic texts are increasingly in demand in education, as they contribute to the realization of educational opportunities, allow for more effective building of the educational process, placing students and teachers at the center of the networked social world. New digital technologies make it possible to solve key educational problems that cannot be solved or are poorly solved on the basis of traditional technologies. Digital technologies provide opportunities to improve the quality of education, the successful functioning of the internal structure of an educational organization, which implies the use of digital resource planning systems, electronic document management. The digital environment of an educational organization requires certain ICT tools that are systematized and meet the requirements of the state standard, which is aimed at more effectively achieving learning outcomes. Effective management of an educational organization assumes that the digital environment should become a common field of interaction for all participants in educational relations, an effective tool for managing the quality of education.

Today, digital educational technologies of massive open online courses have become widespread. Such distance e-learning courses are provided by modern educational organizations for everyone. Such distance e-learning courses are provided by modern educational organizations for everyone. They allow the learner to remotely in any convenient form receive qualified training in a specific narrow area in accordance with his level of knowledge, needs and professional interests.

The digital form of organizing the activities of any educational organization, and therefore a university, becomes a significant indicator that ensures effective functioning, development, competitiveness and relevance. Accordingly, the digital educational environment becomes one of the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of management of an educational organization.

The introduction of digital technologies and digital tools, their use in managing an organization, providing access to digital educational and methodological materials, and expanding the space for creativity contributes to the transition to a model of personalized organization of the educational process.

Digitalization in education is a significant step into the future, but it is obvious that the current stage of digitalization of education will also lead to a change in the traditional appearance and forms of conducting training sessions.

Effective digital transformation is not just about technology. It requires a willingness to embrace technology in new ways beyond the organizational process.

It must be continuous and progressive in order to improve teaching and learning, support existing processes and increase efficiency. The role of the teacher will also change significantly, who will have the opportunity to create their own educational content and form a personal professional profile. As a result of this process, the teacher will turn into a mentor for students, guiding and orienting them within the digital educational space.

An important direction in the education system is the formation of the competitiveness of universities. The main tool for solving this problem is fundamentally new regulatory documents in the field of education (educational standards), which are currently being developed taking into account modern experience in organizing the educational process in leading universities in the world.

When developing new educational standards, the main task is to train modern, highly professional specialists who have the most up-to-date knowledge with analytical and creative thinking, skills in using advanced information and communication technologies and are able to effectively apply all this in their daily practical activities.

The most important area of work in the field of education remains the stimulation of research and innovation activities, the creation of effective mechanisms for introducing scientific and innovative achievements into practice, the creation of scientific and experimental specialized laboratories, high technology centers, and technology parks at higher educational institutions and research institutes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can conclude that at the present stage of development, Uzbekistan is successfully solving strategic tasks of modernizing the entire national education system, introducing modern information and communication technologies, creating a digital educational environment, improving the teaching of foreign languages, forming a new system of postgraduate education, as well as

development of a system for advanced training and retraining of academic and administrative personnel of universities, etc.

Undoubtedly, the implementation of these strategic objectives will ensure the progressive development of the entire system of lifelong education as a single educational-research-production complex based on state and non-state educational institutions, the formation of a competitive environment in the field of education and training, the openness of the system of lifelong education of the republic in the market of educational services, exchange information and specialists, strengthening the international authority of the educational system of Uzbekistan.

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